

Data Management course Notes (26-27.05.2022)

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What are the ways to store your data?

Researchers' opinions:

Suggestion_1: Data are saved in the PC in the lab with an updated copy in the personal laptop, the transfer time happens every one big experiment. A copy of every new set of data is saved in the cloud. Every one month the new updated folder is transferred to a hard device.

Suggestion_2: There are software used to synchronize different PCs related to certain laboratory and the cloud automatically; every time you update a file in a folder it is automatically updated in all other parts of the network.

Science is about sharing our findings with other researchers. In order to do so we can publish the results to be available. On the other hand, you might also want to reconsider and reanalyze or check the raw data to answer your question from a different perspective. Therefore, saving, storing and sharing data are as important as generating and interpreting data.

Data should follow certain kind of standards to be sharable. This criteria lies in the word FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interpretable, Reusable.

Any missing element of these features it reflects a shortage in the research done.

There are different scientific platforms that provide various services including;

- ❖ Galaxy; data analysis platform that provides tools to analyze genomic and proteomic datasets as well as tools for data visualization and clustering. To learn how to use galaxy step by step you can check the following link: <https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/>

I have a personal experience with Galaxy and I highly recommend researchers to learn how to use and include it in your research everyday life.

- ❖ Elixir; It is considered a scientific infrastructure for life sciences providing various services including; data analysis, training, software tools, as well as links and connections to other platforms and organizations (<https://elixir-europe.org/services>)
- ❖ EGA server, European Genome-phenome Archive, it is a scientific repository that is used for permanent storing and sharing human genomic and clinical datasets (<https://ega-archive.org/>)

Data:

- ✓ **Data life cycle:**

During your research you can look at these steps and identify on which level you are at the present, and that could help you prepare for the next step!

✓ **What are data?**

Data are recorded facts.

✓ **What are Data types?**

Numerical, Categorical, images, Sequencing data, Software, Posters, Books, Samples, References

✓ **Metadata:** is structured information about the generated data

Example: 97 is a numerical data, when you add a meaning to it using the unit beats per minute, then the 97 bpm is representing heart rate, which is considered information, through interpreting the findings; that the heart rate = 97bpm this is considered knowledge.

Therefore it is recommended to add meanings and interpretation for the data you are generating or reading and make knowledge out of it to be able to memorize it and use it in your publications.

By the end of the day, try to generate a unit of information:

Read papers related to your research topic, try to summarize the findings presented in the papers using your own words, and most importantly use references. Try also to include all the important details such as the experimental work. This step will help you use these information for publication.

Tip: If you want to memorize information you can create a map or a story representing the topic that is the way our minds are organized and can easily memorize information.

There are certain webpages and platforms that can provide instructions about standards that data should meet to be sharable. Dublin core metadata element set is used as resource for standardized metadata.

Notes: Every single file you generate has metadata file attached to it. Therefore it is recommended to rename a file in case you make changes on it or update it, and **DO NOT** overwrite a document.

It is recommended to name a folder with details using long description more than naming the file this way, meaning that the folder name contains more information than a file name.

- ✓ **Data Lake** contains everything; Databases, videos, social comments, images and you can choose what you want out of it.
- ✓ **Data warehouses** contains structured and filtered data for certain purposes.

Zenodo is a large data repository that can be used for storing and sharing datasets in an unlimited manner.

- ✓ **Research Data Management (RDM)** life cycle describes the process in which research data go through before, after and during research project; including the organization, the laboratory, the repository, funders, publishers, and author contribution.

You can upload documentary data in Zenodo

- ✓ **Software used for publishing and sharing:**

Mendeley, Zotero (free), if you are using Endnote you can export file in an open access format.

Webarchive to archive a webpage, the link can be used as a reference.

Data shared in Zenodo or ORCID repositories can be cited using the DOI.

- ✓ **Zettelkasten method for data management:**

Everyday write a paragraph about your work. At the end of the day you should summarize your notes.

A paragraph composition:

First sentence: it reflects what the reader is expecting to read.

The middle: describes one single idea

The last sentence: So what!! What does that mean?

A paragraph should stand on its own. Delivers one single clear idea.

File management Basics:

✓ **Data organization strategy:**

Be consistent and meaningful

Index your computer and your files: that means your computer is creating a catalog for you file based on certain tags such as the file format.

To check if your files in your computer are indexed; type in the start menu “Indexing options”- Advanced- file types- check index properties only, if it is already checked that means you files are indexed.

Deep indexing of your files

Organized folder:

It is recommended to create organized folders for your research project.

Example:

The main folder is: PhD_project, it contains subfolders;

Conferences

Downloaded_publication

Presentations

Protocols

Experiments

Proposals

Funding

Reports

Manuscripts

Data_analysis_methods_and_protocols

Data_dictionaries: description of the data

In every main folder include a “**Read_me**” file, which describes the content of the folder and subfolders and update it daily.

Do not use space in folders or file names; instead use underscore symbol () or instead start every word with capital letter.

Note: it is recommended to save data in Pdf, CSV, TIFF format but not doc, ppt, or xlsx format the reason is because companies are changing constantly so the file format related to certain

software managed by companies might be affected and thereby increase the probability of data lost.

Another option of documenting your data is by using Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELN)

✓ **Spreadsheet etiquette:**

Do not merge cells; because if you open the excel file in other programs such as R, the content of the excel file will be mixed!

Create a data dictionary: describe data in the dataset

Do not use highlight or color

Subjects in the rows, Variables in the columns, with single heading row

These are the etiquettes which are recommended to be followed, that would make the sharing process easier and faster as you are following certain criteria.

Regarding updating your files, there are certain software for version control that updates your versions automatically.

✓ **Data transformation:**

Data encryption is a method to protect your data. You can encrypt your pendrive, your computer or your hard device. To encrypt your removable device, control panel, System and Security, BitLocker Drive Encryption, Turn On BitLocker, then you will be asked to choose a password, then you will be asked for an alternative location in your computer to save the password in case you forgot it, then start the process, it might take minutes to hours depending on the data size in the device.

To find duplicates; use the DupeGuru program

In clinical datasets before sharing or transferring data, it should be anonymized. Amnesia Dashboard is used for this purpose.

To recover deleted files, you can use Puran File Recovery program.

✓ **Data archiving:**

Re3data.org is used to show which repositories are suitable for each dataset.

Example: if you want to buy a cell line, you type cell line and you get all the available providers, or if you want to order a plasmid; you type addgene which is for plasmid buying access.

DRYAD is a curated data repository; meaning your data can be checked and you will be given feedback. Therefore, you need to pay for using DRYAD.

On the other hand Zenodo is a data repository, with no feedback, and its usage is for free.

If data are deposited in a repository you can still publish it.

IDR is a repository for microscopy images.

In order to apply for a grant, you should submit a data management plan that explains the logistics of your project.